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Battery Cell
Assembly Twin

D4.4: Semantic artefacts, schema alignments and mappings

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Abstract:	<i>This document provides pointers for the results of BatCAT tasks T4.4 and T4.5. The actual D4.4 content (ontologies and mappings) is located in a public GitHub repository. Also, an overview document is provided as an attachment to this file. The major content of these are: the LBCO-Lightweight BatCAT Core Ontologies, their mappings to other ontologies (particularly the EMMO) and to answer set programming.</i>
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Abbreviations and acronyms

ASP	Answer Set Programming
CQ	Competency Question
EMMO	Elementary Multiperspective Material Ontology
GPO	General Process Ontology
IRI	Internationalized Resource Identifier
LBCO	Lightweight BatCAT Core Ontologies
LiB	Lithium-ion battery
OWL	Web Ontology Language
RFB	Redox-flow battery
TTL	Terse Triple Language (Turtle)

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1. Executive summary

BatCAT D4.4, to which this document is associated, concludes the activities of project tasks T4.4 - Metadata standardization and T4.5 - Schema alignment and mapping.

This document serves only as a container/pointer to the main results that constitute D4.4: the LBCO repository located at [1] and the .pdf document “BatCAT ontologies and mappings: an overview”, attached to the present [A1]. See references therein for pointers to the external ontologies and assets they are connected to.

The LBCO set of ontologies has been developed to cover use cases on vanadium redox-flow batteries (RFB) and lithium-ion batteries (LIB). Users of BatCAT tools will be practitioners and operators in manufacturing, modelling and characterization, as well as business managers. Accordingly, LBCO contains concepts that will be used (e.g., for data ingest and decision support) by different actors and tools. They are structured in modules and use light logical expressivity.

The mappings contain two main parts: mapping/alignment to other (non-LBCO) ontologies, and mapping from OWL to ASP. In the first, the main result is the alignment to a set of EMMO-based ontology modules. For the second, the main outcome is a semi-automatic methodology to transform OWL statements in ASP ones. Then, such statements can be used within a logic-based solver.

The activities that led to D4.4 results built strongly on previous work from WP4, namely D4.1 - Data landscape and infrastructure related requirements, especially on the requirements formulated there as competency questions (CQ). Also, strong interactions with other work packages were maintained.

This deliverable, together with the D4.3 Demo [2], concludes the activities of BatCAT WP4. The next project phase will focus on the development of digital twins and decision support systems, which will use LBCO at their core, to support internal and external semantic interoperability of data and components. While the bulk of the LBCO ontologies has concluded, they will be updated at [1] taking into account users’ feedback and evolving requirements from the BatCAT project. With use and as the project development advances and more components / tools need to use them, we expect new requirements will arise.

2. References

[1]. *Lightweight BatCAT Core Ontology (LBCO)* - GitHub repository. <https://github.com/HE-BatCAT/lbco>, 2025.

[2] T. Fitschen et al, *BatCAT D4.3 - Federated knowledge base demo*, video, to appear on Zenodo in December 2025.

3. Annex

[A1]. S. Chiacchiera et al, *BatCAT ontologies and mappings: An overview*, technical report, December 2025.

BatCAT ontologies and mappings: an overview

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Abstract

Within the Horizon Europe project BatCAT (Battery Cell Assembly Twin), a set of ontologies has been developed to cover use cases on vanadium redox-flow batteries and lithium-ion batteries. Users of our tools

will be practitioners and operators in manufacturing, modelling and characterization, as well as business managers. The ontologies in OWL will be the basis for conceptualization at lower and higher logical expressivity (as the YAML data model used within the LinkAhead database and the answer set programming axioms for logic-based optimization). The ontologies will support data ingest and retrieval and semantic interoperability within BatCAT tools and with external components. Here we provide an overview of these ontologies, and of their alignment or mapping to related ones (including BattINFO and the EMMO). Finally we present work on the translation of the ontologies (axioms and facts) from OWL to answer set programming.

1 Introduction

BatCAT¹ considers three major and interconnected aspects of batteries' life cycle: Battery design, battery manufacturing, and battery operation ("in-use"). The central focus of the project is providing a digital twin of battery manufacturing, integrating (physics-based and data-driven) modelling, characterization and sensor data. Two very different types of batteries are considered, vanadium redox-flow batteries (RFBs) and lithium-ion batteries (LiBs).

The main user-facing components will be a knowledge base for batteries, digital twins of both the manufacturing line and batteries in-operando, and an interpretable industrial decision support system (IIDSS). These in turn rely on physics-based and data-driven models, validated and parameterized by characterization data.

Within the IIDSS module, two major types of optimization will be used: Multi-criteria optimization (MCO) and answer set programming (ASP). The first one is suited for numerical optimization, whereas the second targets problems formulated in logical terms, with discrete variables and in a finite domain (e.g., task scheduling, resource allocation, procedural compliance).

A requirements analysis was performed [13] leading to a collection of user stories and a first version of competency questions [6].² To cover all needed concepts, we identified a set of ontology modules, that have been developed: (a) Higher level; (b) Optimization, decision support, design; (c) Twinning; (d) Data and metadata; (e) Modelling and simulation; (f) Characterization; (g) Manufacturing; (h) Battery (LiB and RFB). In parallel, we have evaluated coverage by relevant pre-existing ontologies and standards: these have been used to design mappings and alignments.

In this document we first briefly present the LBCO-Lightweight BatCAT Core Ontologies [7], then their alignment with top-level ontologies, in particular to the EMMO-Elementary Multiperspective Material Ontology. Next we describe an example mapping to GPO-General Process Ontology. Finally we

¹<https://www.batcat.info/>

²In [6] we collected 56 user stories grouped under 23 epics and about 50 competency questions, following the LOT methodology [17]. Also, the relations between characterization methods, characterization devices and measured quantities was given there in tabular form.

Figure 1: Left panel: list of modules and color code used in following figures. Right panel: visual notation adapted from Chowlk (extract) [5].

summarize work to translate OWL axioms and facts into ASP ones, which will serve as a base for the logic-based optimization.

During the course of the project, and as ontology implementation proceeded, the initial competency questions have been updated: the current ones and their mapping to LBCO ontology entities is given in App. A.

2 LBCO modules

The set of modules under development is called LBCO – Lightweight BatCAT Core Ontologies. They are written in OWL (in Turtle format), starting by design from lower logical expressivity, then increasing complexity iteratively and only if motivated by application needs. The development is done in a public GitHub repository [7]. All modules (b) - (h) are aligned with (a), however some are vertical [(e) - (g)] and other transversal [(b) - (d) and (h)]: this means that, for example, the data module (e.g., describing uncertainties and data quality protocols) needs to address corresponding issues from modelling, characterization and manufacturing. In Figure 1, we list the modules and give the graphical notation used in the repository. In the rest of this section we give the scope of each module. Beside the individual modules, for convenience, the repository contains also a file with all LBCO modules³.

Higher level concepts (higher.ttl)

A module to facilitate a structuring of and connection between the lower modules, and a possible alignment of LBCO with top level ontologies. In Figure 2 we show its class structure.

³https://github.com/HE-BatCAT/lbco/blob/main/all_LBCO_modules_combined/all_lbco_modules_combined.ttl

Figure 2: Classes in the `higher.ttl` module, version dating December 2025. This and similar figures were generated using the Protégé tool [15], see also <https://protege.stanford.edu/>.

Modelling and simulation (`modelling.ttl`)

A module about computational modelling and related processes, as model parametrization and validation, and the involved data.

Characterization (`characterization.ttl`)

Focuses on off-line characterization. On-line characterization (i.e., that is integrated with the manufacturing process itself, e.g., via sensors) is addressed in the manufacturing module.

Manufacturing (`manufacturing.ttl`)

A module about manufacturing of products, via intermediate ones. Includes on-line characterization (i.e., sensors), actuators, product and process KPIs.

Optimization, decision support, design (`optimization.ttl`)

A module about optimization problems, either numerical or logic-based. It allows to state a problem and its solution.

Twinning (`twinning.ttl`)

A module about twinning, a particular type of computational modelling. In fact, digital twinning in particular involves models (typically data-driven, or hybrid, but not necessarily) that are synchronized with the physical world making use of sens or or characterization data. It allows to describe the twin functionalities.

Data and metadata (data.ttl)

A module about (meta)data aspects, such as uncertainties, data quality protocols, and metadata schemas used to annotate data.

Battery (LiB and RFB) (battery.ttl)

A module containing all the battery specific information, such as battery manufacturing processes and battery product parts. Two major types of batteries are considered: Lithium-ion batteries and redox-flow batteries. This module is by far the largest of LBCO, as it expands on many of the different dimensions tackled by the others.

2.1 LBCO evaluation

The LBCO ontologies have been evaluated using OOPS! [18] and FOOPS! [11] tools: the first one detected no critical warning, and the second one gave a score larger than 60 % using the “File” modality. Use of these tools on previous versions has helped us improve the ontology quality and FAIRness. We note that the current FOOPS! tool is a development (beta) version, so the numerical score is to be viewed in that light.⁴

2.2 LBCO Accessibility and persistence

The LBCO ontologies, alongside their mappings discussed in this document, are available in a public GitHub repository [7]. The persistent URL <https://purl.org/lbco> and the URI <https://batcat.info/semantics/core> both redirect to [7].

3 Related work

There is a large amount of literature on digital twins in industry and on battery digitalization: we cite here only the most relevant for our work.

Specific to batteries, we highlight the Battery interface ontology (BattINFO) [8] (a collection of EMMO domain modules, cf. Sec. 4.1), the Battery Value Chain Ontology (BVCO) [8], that describes manufacturing steps and their inputs and outputs. For digital twins, the standard ISO 30173:2023 [14] provides a reference vocabulary, and Barros *et al.* [2] analyzes requirements and suggests an ontology addressing them. To describe sensors and actuators, the W3C Semantic Sensor Network (SSN) [19] is available. For characterization data, the CHAMEO ontology [16], is an ontologization of the CHADA CEN Workshop Agreement [4].

⁴E.g., we noted an issue that we believe arises when domain and range are used in parallel with restrictions on some property, causing some misreading of the ontology and an artificial score reduction. This is to be further tested and explored, first on our side, and then in connection with the FOOPS! tool developers if needed.

Previous work by some of us within the VIMMP - Virtual Materials Marketplace project includes ontologies for software (VISO - VIMMP Software Ontology) and variables (VOV - VIMMP Ontology of Variables), which are tailored to materials modelling software and algorithms [12], with a focus on physics-based modelling. We note that `higher.ttl` bears similarities with the higher level module developed there (EVMPO - European Virtual Marketplace Ontology).

All of the above has informed our developments at different levels (e.g., coverage analysis, drawing direct connections).

4 Alignment of the BatCAT “Higher” ontology with EMMO

The concepts in the BatCAT LBCO “higher” ontology have been aligned with the EMMO 1.0.2 ontology, available via <https://w3id.org/emmo/1.0.2>. The alignment file is available in the dedicated folder⁵.

The key EMMO concepts to which the BatCAT classes have been aligned are:

1. Objects and Processes, which are the highest level concepts in the EMMO Persistence Perspective.
2. Data and Information, which are high level concepts in the EMMO Contrast Perspective.
3. Material, which belongs to the EMMO core concepts based on its materialistic foundation. We have chosen Material, rather than the more generic Substance class, as BatCAT deals with specific materials for manufacturing (i.e. for a certain purpose).
4. Property, which in EMMO belongs to the Semiotics Perspective, and
5. Role, which can be found in the EMMO Holistic Perspective.

In more detail:

- With the EMMO Persistence Perspective, we aligned
 - LBCO:Physical Object in equivalent to emmo:Object. As a result, the subclasses on the BatCAT Physical Object, i.e. Sample and Device, are also subclasses of emmo:Object. That is consistent with similar subclasses in EMMO and its domain ontologies. In particular emmo:Device is a subclass of emmo: ManufacturedProduct which is a subclass of emmo:Object.

⁵<https://github.com/HE-BatCAT/lbco/blob/main/alignment/alignment-with-ecb.ttl>

Figure 3: Extract of the EMMO Persistence Perspective.

- LBCO:Agent is a subclass of emmo:agent. The latter is elucidated as “A participant that is the driver of a process.” Any such “driver”, whether machine, human, animal, etc is an emmo:agent, whereas the LBCO:agent is the disjoint union of human and machine agents, hence the subclass relation was chosen.
- LBCO:Process, while not further elucidated is assumed to have the same semantic meaning as emmo:process. For the latter, the requirement is that there must be at least 2 temporal parts which are not of the same type, signifying change. Hence the equivalence relation is used.
- LBCO:Method. We interpret the method class in LBCO as subclass of emmo:Procedure, where the latter is described as “an intentional process with a plan.” Procedure subclasses in EMMO include Measurement and Computation, which seems to align well with the LBCO subclasses of characterisation and modelling/simulation methods.

The relevant EMMO class hierarchy is shown in Figure 3.

- In the EMMO Contrast Perspective (which includes emmo:data, emmo:information and emmo:software), we aligned:
 - LBCO:data are interpreted as being equivalent to emmo:data
 - LBCO:statement and LBCO:annotation are subclasses of emmo:information. This means that in an emmo-aligned and integrated ontology, statement and annotation would become subclasses of LBCO:data rather than sitting alongside it.
 - LBCO:software as a subclass of emmo:software. Here we used the subclass relation because the LBCO software typically refers to application programs. In contrast, emmo:software also includes the source code files for example.

An image of the relevant EMMO class hierarchy is shown in Figure 4.

- In the EMMO Holistic Perspective, we aligned:

Figure 4: Extract of the EMMO Contrast Perspective.

- LBCO:role as equivalent to emmo:role. The implication is that in an EMMO aligned system, the role involves a parthood relation with respect to an overall ‘whole’ in which it participates. For example, hammer is a role that can be fulfilled by many objects (not just those labelled ‘hammer’, but always requires a process (“hammering”) in which the hammer participates. Outside of this process, the ‘hammer’ is an object.
- LBCO:material is equivalent to emmo:material, which is “an amount of ordinary matter substance (or mixture of substances) in different states of matter or phases”, and “usually means some definite kind, quality, or quantity of matter, especially as intended for use.”

The alignment file can be found in the LBCO repository “alignment” folder.

4.1 Integrated EMMO-based ecosystem of ontologies as reference ontologies for BatCAT

Work within previous European projects, notably BIG-MAP⁶ and NanoMECommons⁷, has led to the creation of a set of interoperable modules for different facets of batteries and materials characterisation, respectively. Building on these ontologies, which largely align to the EMMO (Elementary Multiperspective Material Ontology)⁸, an integrated ontology (in turtle format) of required EMMO top- and middle level modules and domain ontologies has been created and placed in the BatCAT github repository “external” folder⁹ as a reference containing a number of relevant domain concepts for further alignment and integration with BatCAT ontologies.

⁶<https://www.big-map.eu/>

⁷<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/952869>

⁸<https://github.com/emmo-repo/EMMO>

⁹<https://github.com/HE-BatCAT/lbco/blob/main/external/ecb-inferred.ttl>. This is the integrated, inferred version of the EMMO, Battery, Electrochemistry, Chemical Substance and BTO ontologies (named ECB). In the same folder there is also the corresponding, very compact, asserted version (“ecb-asserted.ttl”). For the sake of comprehensiveness, a ZIP file with all of the ontology modules making up the integrated version (in the external/ecb-ontologies subfolder) is also given.

Figure 5: Graphical overview of the integrated EMMO-based system of ontologies, cf. Sec. 4.1.

The included ontologies are as follows (and can be found separately in the github repository <https://github.com/emmo-repo>):

- domain-battery (Battery Domain Ontology)
- domain-chemical-substance
- domain-electrochemistry
- domain-characterisation-methodology (CHAMEO)
- application-battery-testing-ontology (BTO).

In the process, the alignment of the domain ontologies has been upgraded to emmo 1.0.2 and a few small bugs/mis-alignments have been addressed.

A graphical overview of this integrated EMMO-based system on ontologies is shown Figure 5.

5 Mappings of LBCO to external ontologies: example of GPO, for manufacturing steps

During the course of the BatCAT project, we have compared our requirements with existing relevant ontologies. As a result, mappings have been produced, as for example that of manufacturing steps from LBCO to GPO¹⁰. For completeness, we also give a snapshot of the used version of GPO in the “external” folder.

The purpose of such mappings is to enable data conversion between data annotated using LBCO and those using GPO. We note that here and in similar cases, we opted for duplicating classes to avoid dependencies on external efforts.

For the specific case of battery manufacturing steps, the LBCO contains information about input, output and settings of each step. Analog comparison work has been done for other key concepts (including, e.g., substances from

¹⁰<https://github.com/HE-BatCAT/lbco/blob/main/mappings/map2gpo.ttl>

EMMO and characterization techniques from CHAMEO) and will be added to the LBCO repository in the future.

6 Mapping of LBCO extracts to answer set programming (ASP)

The genuine advantage of ASP lies in its high-level modelling language, which is based on first-order logic and separates specific instance data from high-level problem encodings [3]. This expressivity makes ASP attractive for modelling complex and diverse application problems [9], particularly including configuration, planning and scheduling tasks [10] similar to those to be addressed within the BatCAT project. For performing optimization, ASP solving systems implement dedicated strategies for optimizing a single objective function or several lexicographically ordered criteria [1].

In the “mappings/map2asp” folder¹¹ of [7] we detail the methodology developed within BatCAT for the semi-automatic conversion from OWL/TTL to ASP. Also, we give concrete examples, to demonstrate possible applications of ASP and its connection to the BatCAT ontologies.

An optimization example

The *(method) selection example* illustrates a typical situation that could manifest as part of Design of Simulation or Design of Experiment: different (experimental and modelling) methods can be used to assess certain observable quantities of interest. As the available methods differ in their attributes (e.g., cost, precision), optimal solutions will be suggested based on the user-defined criteria.

To this end, the ontology module(s) describing the methods are automatically converted into facts in the input language of the ASP solving system `clingo`¹². They are augmented with auxiliary facts for parameterizing the optimization objectives to apply, e.g., maximizing the precision, as primary criterion, and secondarily minimizing the cost of a selected method. A general problem encoding specifies hard constraints and optimization objectives in terms of first-order rules, which are evaluated by `clingo` for the facts at hand in order to compute an optimal solution.

7 Conclusion

We have presented here the BatCAT ontologies and their relation to other efforts in the ontology landscape. Also, work to relate them and ontologies more in general to answer set programming has been summarized. While the bulk of the development of LBCO ontologies has concluded, they will be updated

¹¹<https://github.com/HE-BatCAT/lbco/tree/main/mappings/map2asp>

¹²<https://potassco.org/clingo/>

Property	Values
Prefix	CQ=Competency Question, EQ=Example Query, FA=Fact
Area(s)	EXP=Experiment, SIM=Simulation, MAN=Manufacturing, DAT=Data , CRO=cross-area

Table 1: Properties and values of tags used for CQs, FAs and EQs in Table 2.

at [7] taking into account users’ feedback and evolving requirements from the BatCAT project. With use and as the project development advances and more components / tools need to use them, we expect new requirements will arise.

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A Competency Questions for LBCO

Here we report in Table 2 the requirements implemented in the LBCO ontology, expressed mainly in the forms of *competency question* (CQ), but also as *natural language sentence (fact)* (FA), and *example query* (EQ). For each requirement, we indicate the IRI of the most relevant corresponding LBCO entities (classes and properties). The questions listed here correspond to those on the LBCO repository as of 16 Decemeber 2025¹³. Requirements are tagged using the properties given in Table 1 (prefix and area).

We underline that LBCO ontologies contain more concepts and patters than those captured in Table 2, however this list of 37 requirements captures major ones. Finally, we note that the numbering of the tags is kept as it was in [6] for the entries that have been kept or minimally modified with respect to that version. Additions / removals have taken place after September 2024, and the numbering is not always sequential as requirements that have been superseded and/or not implemented are not reported here. The list is dynamic and will be kept updated in [7], and synchronized with the ontologies.

¹³https://github.com/HE-BatCAT/lbco/blob/main/doc/competency_questions.csv

ID	Competency Question (CQ) / Natural language sentence (fact) (FA) / Example Query (EQ)	Answer [for CQ only]	IRI of LBCO most relevant classes/properties
CQ_CRO_1	What are the main properties of the electrode?	surface chemical composition; surface area; conductivity; surface hydrophilicity; exchange current rate; tortuosity; porosity; surface stability (towards modifications)	lbco:electrode; lbco:has_property
CQ_CRO_2	What are the main properties of the electrolyte?	Composition (salts; solvents); purity; transport properties (viscosity; ionic conductivity); mass density	lbco:electrolyte; lbco:has_property
CQ_CRO_3	What are the major time scales for process industry? (to classify various types of DTs)	Industrial safety; intermediate; planning	lbco:time_scale
CQ_CRO_4	What are the main components of a RFB?	Bipolar plates; Membranes; Carbon felt; Electrolyte	lbco:redox_flow_battery; lbco:has_part
CQ_CRO_4.1	What are the main components of a LiB/NiB?	Active material; Binder; Percolant; Slurry solvent; Electrode; Separator; Electrolyte; Collector; Battery cell; Casing; Coating layer; Full cell	lbco:lithium_ion_battery; lbco:has_part
CQ_CRO_8	What are the high-level types of optimization problems that can benefit from logic-based approaches?	Scheduling (e.g. of maintenance); Allocation of resources (e.g. machines/humans for tasks); Compatibility checks (e.g. between materials); Compliance (e.g. of a process with regulation); Process design (e.g. simulation / experiment); Process sequence validation (e.g. that the ordering of sub-processes does not break dependencies)	lbco:logic_based_problem

Continued on next page...

Table 2 – ... continued from previous page

ID	Competency Question (CQ) / Natural language sentence (fact) (FA) / Example Query (EQ)	Answer [for CQ only]	IRI of LBCO most relevant classes/properties
CQ_CRO_9	What are the main scales for processes in RFB?	Molecular scale; Fiber scale; Pore scale; Cell scale; Stack scale; Battery system scale; Energy system scale	lbc:rfb_length_scale
FA_CRO_3	Materials incompatibilities need to be pointed out (e.g. mixtures that are unsafe)	n/a - fact	lbc:is_incompatible_with; lbc:is_material_incompatible_with_material
FA_CRO_4	A sample or a product belong to a batch	n/a - fact	lbc:batch
CQ_DAT_3.2	What method is used to process the raw data (and obtain processed data)?	Conversion; extraction; incomplete dataset removal; incomplete dataset padding	lbc:has_data_processing_method; lbc:has_data_processing_info; lbc:data_processing_method
CQ_DAT_1	Is the data(set) complete with respect to a given data structure?	Yes; No	lbc:is_complete_dataset
CQ_DAT_2	Does the data(set) contain dummy values?	Yes; No	lbc:contains_dummy_values
CQ_DAT_4	What types of data quality evaluation methods (checks/guarantees) are available within BatCAT?	Human assessment; Quality insurance procedures (e.g. regular calibration checks); Automated repeatability tests	lbc:data_quality_evaluation_method
CQ_DAT_5	What is the average value and error of property X over a certain set?	n/a - case-specific	lbc:data; lbc:has_average; lbc:has_error
CQ_DAT_7	What methods are available in BatCAT to quantify uncertainties in general?	Error propagation; Error estimate via statistical methods	lbc:uncertainty_quantification_method

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Table 2 – ... continued from previous page

ID	Competency Question (CQ) / Natural language sentence (fact) (FA) / Example Query (EQ)	Answer [for CQ only]	IRI of LBCO most relevant classes/properties
CQ_DAT_8	What metadata schemas are used to annotate datasets to ensure FAIR compliance?	n/a - case specific	lbc:is_annotated_using_scheme
CQ_EXP_3.3	What are the high-level types of characterization needed for RFB or LiB?	Electrochemical characterization; Physicochemical characterization; Rheological characterization	lbc:electrochemical_characterization_technique; lbc:physicochemical_characterization_technique; lbc:rheological_characterization_technique
FA_EXP_1	A characterization technique involves a sample + some instrument (characterization device) and evaluates (as output) some physical quantities	n/a - fact	lbc:characterization_technique
CQ_MAN_3	What are the main properties of a sensor?	type/measured variable; connection type (WIFI/Bluetooth; Optical fiber; wired electrical cable)	lbc:sensor; lbc:observes; lbc:property; lbc:has_connection; lbc:connection
CQ_MAN_3.2	What are the sensor types for on-line characterization of LIB?	Accelerometer; Temperature sensor (Thermocouple); vibration sensor; Gas-detection sensor (CO / CO2 sensor); Power sensor (Power monitoring clip); pressure sensor	lbc:sensor
CQ_MAN_4	What are the main (manufacturing) quantities to monitor (process KPIs)?	Energy consumption; Equipment performance; Waste produced (amount); Product quality	lbc:manufacturing_process; lbc:has_process_kpi
CQ_MAN_5.1	What are the main ordered steps in the LIB/NIB manufacturing process?	Mixing; Coating; Drying; Calendaring; Cutting; Assembling; Filling; Forming; Degassing	lbc:lib_manufacturing_process_step

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Table 2 – ... continued from previous page

ID	Competency Question (CQ) / Natural language sentence (fact) (FA) / Example Query (EQ)	Answer [for CQ only]	IRI of LBCO most relevant classes/properties
CQ_MAN_5.2	What are the main ordered steps in the RFB manufacturing process?	Stack assembly; Stack compression; Stack sealing (glueing); Tanks assembling	lbc:rfb_manufacturing_process_step
CQ_MAN_6.1	What are the LIB/NIB battery (product) design parameters?	Active material (choice); Electrolyte Formulation; Particle size distribution; Electrolyte composition; Separator; Cell size	lbc:has_product_design_parameter
CQ_MAN_6.2	What are the RFB battery (product) design parameters?	Current density; Ion species concentration; Electrode base material; Volume flow rate; Cell size (Product dimensions)	lbc:has_product_design_parameter
CQ_MAN_7.3	What are the control/process parameters (=settings) of the LIB/NIB manufacturing process in BatCAT?	Mixing order; Mixing speed; Cutting shape; Cutting size; Calendering speed; Calendering temperature; Calendering thickness; Coating speed; Coating targeted area capacity; Wet coating gap	lbc:lib_manufacturing_process_step; lbc:has_setting
CQ_MAN_7.4	What are the control/process parameters (=settings) of the RFB manufacturing process in BatCAT?	Furnace temperature; Furnace atmosphere composition; Time at furnace; Cooling time	lbc:rfb_manufacturing_process_step; lbc:has_setting
CQ_MAN_8.1	What are the variables to evaluate (=process KPIs) the LIB/NIB manufacturing process?	Scrap rate; Production cost per unit	lbc:lib_manufacturing_process; lbc:has_process_kpi
CQ_MAN_8.2	What are the variables to evaluate (=process KPIs) the RFB manufacturing process?	Production performance; Production cost per unit; Throughput failure rate	lbc:rfb_manufacturing_process; lbc:has_process_kpi

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ID	Competency Question (CQ) / Natural language sentence (fact) (FA) / Example Query (EQ)	Answer [for CQ only]	IRI of LBCO most relevant classes/properties
CQ_MAN_9.1	What are the LIB/NIB battery product main properties (KPIs)?	Full cell Initial performance; Full cell Ageing; Full cell Safety	lbco:lithium_ion_battery; lbco:has_product_kpi
CQ_MAN_9.2	What are the RFB battery product main properties (KPIs)?	Full cell efficiency; Full cell Capacity; Full cell Durability	lbco:redox_flow_battery; lbco:has_product_kpi
CQ_MAN_10	What are other general input parameters (settings) of the manufacturing process?	Electricity unit cost; Personnel unit cost	lbco:manufacturing_process; lbco:has_setting
CQ_SIM_6	What is the range of applicability of a given Model (Digital Twin)?	n/a - case specific	lbco:has_applicability_range_info
CQ_SIM_9	What type of reproducibility tests are available in general for modelling data?	Varying modelling approach; Varying numerical method; varying software	lbco:model_reproducibility_method
FA_SIM_1	Neural network models can be classified by the dimensionality of input and output fed to the neural network	n/a - fact	lbco:has_nn_input_dimensionality; lbco:has_nn_output_dimensionality; lbco:neural_network_model
EQ_SIM_2	What data was used to define this model parametrization?	n/a - answer will be case specific	lbco:model_parametrization_process; lbco:has_input
EQ_SIM_3	What data was used to validate this model parametrization?	n/a - answer will be case specific	lbco:model_validation_process; lbco:has_input

Table 2: Requirements for LBCO expressed in the form of competency question, natural language sentence (“fact”) and example query. This list matches that available on LBCO Github on 16 December 2025.

B Acronyms

We list in the following main acronyms used throughout the text.

ASP: Answer Set Programming; **CQ:** Competency Question; **EMMO:** Elementary Multiperspective Material Ontology; **GPO:** General Process Ontology; **IRI:** Internationalized Resource Identifier; **KPI:** Key performance indicator; **LBCO:** Lightweight BatCAT Core Ontologies ; **LiB:** Lithium-ion battery; **NiB:** Sodium-ion battery; **OWL:** Web Ontology Language; **RFB:** Redox-flow battery; **TTL:** Terse Triple Language (Turtle).

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